

Problem-based Teaching and Learning and Authentic Assessment of Mathematics for First-year Engineering Students

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Abstract

Engineering higher education has undergone and continues to undergo enormous change over the past decade and a half. Features of ‘emerging leaders’ in this trend are noted as having a curricular emphasis on, among other aspects, student-centred, active learning. The New Model Institute for Technology and Engineering (NMITE), itself represents an emerging leader in the UK.

Given this changing landscape, it is important to consider how mathematics embeds within engineering education; this itself is an emerging field of research. This paper is a case study, showing how mathematics was embedded into a first-year thermodynamics module at NMITE, with the aim of promoting discussion in the sector around the pedagogic rationale behind such an approach.

Presented here are the underlying pedagogic principles to mathematics education at NMITE, followed by a description of the practices involved in embedding mathematics into a first-year thermodynamics module. Findings show a broadly positive student experience with mathematics embedment in the module. The attainment data did not provide statistically significant effect sizes by whether students possessed a prior FHEQ Level 3 mathematics qualification.

Introduction

The New Model Institute for Technology and Engineering (NMITE), a self-described ‘disruptor’ (Hitt, et al., 2020), offers a distinctive approach to teaching and learning in the UK higher education sector. Among its differentiating qualities include:

Problem-based, challenge-led learning – Learning in each NMITE module is driven by an industry-provided challenge, reflecting what students might encounter as professional engineers. This provides a basis for learning facilitation which itself is problem-based.

Block teaching – All modules at NMITE are ran in blocks, i.e. are not taught concurrently with other modules over the course of a semester.

9-5 studio-based learning – Groups of no more than 30 students are taught face-to-face in a studio environment, enabling a collaborative learning space, more representative of an engineering workplace than a traditional lecture hall or seminar room.

Embedded academic skills delivery – ‘Academic skills’ (namely mathematical, communicational, digital and professional) are embedded in module learning content and assessment, as opposed to being taught via pre-requisite, for example, ‘mathematics’ or ‘employability’ modules. This appears as 5 credits in every module and are planned by

the Academic Skills and Knowhow (ASK) Centre. Additionally, as is common in the sector (Lawson, Grove, & Croft, 2020), the ASK provides out-of-module elective support.

Inclusive student recruitment – Unlike most undergraduate engineering programmes, NMITE students do not require a Framework for Higher Education Qualifications (FHEQ) level 3 qualification in mathematics or physics to be enrolled (Graham, 2018).

The teaching and learning of mathematics for engineers is itself an emerging field of research, sitting in a niche cross-section of mathematics and engineering pedagogy (Pepin, Biehler, & Gueudet, 2021). Naturally, mathematics education at NMITE is underpinned by the institution's wider pedagogy. In producing 'work ready' engineers, it follows that mathematics be taught and assessed in a way that reflects what a professional engineer's experience may be with it. As highlighted by Goold (2012), 'mathematical thinking' is of superior relevance to professional engineers in their work than 'curriculum mathematics'. Definitions range, but one perspective presented by Schoenfeld (1992) identifies mathematical thinking as 'developing a mathematical point of view' and 'mathematical sense-making'. This contrasts with curriculum mathematics, which can be understood as the topics/domains of mathematics as they appear in the university curriculum. Building on this, mathematics education at NMITE emphasises mathematical thinking. As outlined by Verhage and de Lange (1997), mathematical thinking or 'mathematisation' is considered a higher-order thinking skill, as opposed to the lower-order thinking skill of reproducing algorithms and techniques.

It is well established that a constructivist, student-centred approach to teaching and learning, which emphasises the learner making sense of mathematical problems in their own way, is preferable for developing creative and higher-order thinking skills (Brooks & Brooks, 1999). Accordingly, mathematics at NMITE, as in the rest of its teaching and learning delivery, is predominantly a constructivist, problem-based approach.

A Learning Plan for Mathematics Embedment

The principles detailed above are reflected in the ASK learning plan for mathematics embedment into the FHEQ level 4 'Thermodynamics and Fluids' module. The time-based plan, outlined in Table 2, has two sections: Sessions 1-4 focus on a formative assessment, while Sessions 5-7 prepare students for a summative assessment.

In Session 1-4, the ASK was able to satisfy the learning outcomes of its own 'maths thread' running across the programme. The formative assessment required students to email a descriptive solution to the 'Silo Problem' that involved determining the dimensions of a liquid storage silo with diagrams showing how it may drain. The summative assessment was split into two stages. Stage 1 mirrored the formative assessment, requiring an emailed solution to a modelling and mass balance problem. Stage 2 was an open-book paper test on core module principles, with a generous completion time.

The learning plan contains a range of standard mathematical topics, including quadratics, simultaneous equations, basic calculus, and assumptions and approximation as problem-solving mechanisms. Skills-based learning facilitation was provided: using Microsoft Equation Editor; simple digital diagram-making and using online tools (e.g. Symbolab, ChatGPT, Wolfram Alpha). A key aim in designing the learning plan was to address students' relationships with and preconceptions about mathematics. This includes addressing issues of mindset and anxiety relating to mathematics (Boaler, 2024); critical openness towards use of digital tools and generative artificial intelligence to support problem-solving; and challenging the notion that there is only ever one valid approach and solution to mathematical problems.

Table 1 - Tabulated learning plan for mathematics embedment in the Thermodynamics and Fluids module

Teaching Objectives	Mathematical Topic(s) / Student Progress with Problem(s)
<p><u>Session 1: Introduction to Module and Silo Problem</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop students' familiarity with how taught sessions will work (explain problem-based learning) • Set expectations by emphasising resilient mindset towards difficult problems and encourage students to take their own unique approaches to problem-solving • Send Silo Problem emails, written such that each student receives unique specifications for their silo • Demonstrate how to translate a written problem statement into mathematical equations/ideas • Demonstrate when systems of equations are not solvable (informal degrees of freedom analysis) • Encourage students to use digital problem-solving tools (Symbolab, ChatGPT, Wolfram Alpha) • Show students how to use the Microsoft Equation Editor in drafting an email response 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mathematisation • Degrees of Freedom • Simultaneous Equations • Digital Equation Writing
<p><u>Session 2: Diagramming and Differentiation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task students with using the dimensions from the previous session to create labelled drawings of their liquid storage silos, using a variety of suggested digital tools (Miro, Figma, MS PowerPoint, Canva) • Task students with estimating rates of change on graphs provided via A3 handouts • Suggest a more accurate means of determining instantaneous rates of change, namely, differentiation. Deliver interactive presentation on differentiation, with emphasis on conceptual understanding. Procedural understanding reinforced via 'quickfire round' problems • Demonstrate how students may define a function for their respective graph, then differentiate to provide more accurate solutions to earlier estimates • Introduce students to idea of liquid storage silo drainage flow as a derivative, namely $Q = \frac{dV}{dt}$ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diagramming • Graphical Interpretation • Graph Fitting / Function Modelling • Differentiation
<p><u>Session 3: Integration</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repeat of Session 2, but with focus on accumulation of quantities and integration • Derive a differential equation describing change in fluid volume as silo is drained and emphasise use of integration as means of solving it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphical Interpretation • Graph Fitting / Function Modelling • Integration • Students have a differential equation describing silo drainage

Teaching Objectives	Mathematical Topic(s) / Student Progress with Problem(s)
<p><u>Session 4: Box With a Hole in It Practical</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate how the differential equation from Session 3 may be solved and use as a basis to introduce an equation describing how a given box (physically shown) may theoretically drain • Introduce the idea of a ‘discharge coefficient’, which may be inserted into the equation to bridge the gap from how the box drains in theory, and how the box drains in practice • Lead students to a new setting, where students are tasked with determining the discharge coefficient in the ‘box with a hole in it’ scenario, which involves the production and solving of a quadratic equation • Reemphasise formative submission deadline, as at this stage students have everything they need to complete the assessment task 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solving Differential Equations • Experimental Design • Quadratics <p>• Students have a discharge coefficient value, which may be used in their Silo Problem formative assignment submissions</p> <p>• Formative submission deadline reemphasised</p>
<p><u>Sessions 5 & 6: Mass Balance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate students’ learning of how to approach mass balance problems, Session 5 on single-unit problems, and Session 6 multi-unit problems • Draw on learning from Session 1, and deliver an interactive presentation on degrees of freedom analysis, this time with explicit reference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degrees of Freedom • Simultaneous Equations <p>• Students learn how to approach mass balance problems, which will be one focus of the summative assignment</p>
<p><u>Session 7: Assumptions and Approximation for Problem Solving</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocate students a set of problems, where solving necessarily requires them to define unprovided information, namely, to make assumptions • Deliver interactive presentation on ‘assumptions’ as a problem-solving tool, also emphasising approximation • Task students with approximation problems, for instance, estimating the rate of cocoa butter production expected from a cocoa bean plantation with pre-defined land area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assumption Making • Approximation <p>• Students learn how to approach approximate modelling problems, which will be another focus of summative assignment</p> <p>• Students have all they need for summative assessment preparation</p>

Findings and Discussion

A key aim for the ASK at FHEQ level 4 is to minimise the performance gap between students with and without a prior FHEQ level 3 mathematics qualification. Beyond level 4 students' grades contribute to final degree classifications, meaning a significant performance gap may undermine fairness and widening participation. Table 3 summarises attainment gaps between the two groups, alongside one-sided p-values from Mann-Whitney U tests ($\alpha = 0.05$). The results of the Mann-Whitney U tests failed to reject the null hypothesis that enrolment with a FHEQ level 3 mathematics qualification has no influence on attainment.

Table 2 - Mean grades from summative tutorial questions assessment, grouped by students with and without a prior FHEQ level 3 mathematics qualification

	Mean Grade Without FHEQL3 Mathematics Qualification	Mean Grade With FHEQL3 Mathematics Qualification	Delta	Mann-Whitney U one-sided p-value
Stage 1	60.2%	62.4%	2.2%	26.1%
Stage 2	47.7%	53.1%	5.4%	14.6%
Overall	51.5%	55.9%	4.4%	23.5%

One month after completion of the module, all 39 participating students were contacted to gather feedback. Of those, 19 students (49%) completed a survey, and 7 (18%) elected to also take part in an in-person conversation about the mathematical elements of the module. A graphical summary of the quantitative data from the feedback survey is given in Figure 3.

Figure 1 – Graphical summary of quantitative data from student feedback survey

The majority of the students who attended the conversation were individuals who have expressed concerns of their mathematical skills. Hence it was particularly pleasing that their reflections were broadly positive. The questions asked were open-ended and included:

What mathematical topics or elements did you find challenging?
What mathematical elements did you find enjoyable? Or not enjoyable?
Can you recall the mathematical topics that were covered in this module?
Did the mathematics in this module 'feel' different to maths in other modules?

All named the Silo Problem and the Box with a Hole in It practical as being particularly enjoyable: "It was just great!", "I liked how it made me think", "oooh, I wonder how this, say that the base of the box was not perfectly flat, affects the flow rate." Students also noted the way these activities were organised: "You didn't tell us - you showed us how to do these problems", "They were very well-planned", "I could see an end goal and why we were doing the maths", "You gave me a reason to care about maths." Some mentioned other topics: "The mass balance problems were really fun! ... They were like solving an incomplete puzzle."

In exploring the covered maths topics, it was revealing to hear some students explain 'Assumptions and Approximations' was "not really maths", or that "this session was about something bigger than maths". Others differed: "I liked that it was making your own maths", "There were no given formula which was interesting." They also identified aspects of maths that were not part of the formal learning plan, such as geometry. One student seemed surprised that they were now looking forward to more maths, "I am excited to continue calculus in other modules"; another noted, "I am not elated about maths, but I won't mind."

Conclusion

This paper introduces the pedagogical principles underpinning teaching and learning at NMITE, an emerging leader in UK engineering higher education. NMITE's approach to mathematics education is outlined, and its practical application is exemplified via a detailed learning plan for mathematics embedment in an FHEQ level 4 thermodynamics module.

Evaluation of the learning plan, through attainment and student feedback analysis, yielded largely positive findings, with interesting perceptions of mathematics and on what they felt they had learnt. Attainment data showed insignificant attainment gaps between students with and without a prior FHEQ level 3 mathematics qualification, while feedback suggested broadly positive learning experiences with the mathematical elements of the module.

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